

Questionnaires

Hourly Self-report

[Answered on Smartwatch]

1. Rate your own productivity for the past hour
[7-point Likert-type scale: 1=very low, 7= very high; and option 'I didn't work']
2. How much time did you spend on your own tasks in the past hour?
[5-point likert scale; 1=none at all, 2=a little, 3=a moderate amount, 4=a lot, 5=a great deal]
3. How much did you help your team in the past hour?
[5-point Likert scale; 1=not at all, 2=a little, 3=a moderate amount, 4=a lot, 5=a great deal]
4. Rate how well you spent your time for the past hour
[7-point Likert-type scale: 1=very poorly, 2=poorly, 3=slightly poorly, 4=neutral, 5=slightly well, 6=well, 7=very well]

Self-reports can be postponed for 1 hour, 2 hours, until the next day (morning), or until the next week (Monday). Users choose a rating using the scroll wheel of the watch.

Daily Diary

1. How would you rate your overall productivity today?
[7-point Likert-type scale: 1=very low, 7= very high; and option 'I didn't work']
Below is a visualization of your productivity today:
2. How much time did you spend on your own tasks today? [5-point likert scale; 1=none at all, 2=a little, 3=a moderate amount, 4=a lot, 5=a great deal]
3. How much time did you spend on helping your team today? [5-point likert scale; 1=none at all, 2=a little, 3=a moderate amount, 4=a lot, 5=a great deal]
4. How much of your work was towards organizational goals today (that is, goals that your organization has that are not part of your core work on your squads or value stream mission)?
[5-point likert scale; 1=none at all, 2=a little, 3=a moderate amount, 4=a lot, 5=a great deal]
5. How did you choose what to work on today? [text entry]
6. If you helped your team or organization today, how do you think it affected your productivity?
[very negatively, fairly negatively, somewhat negatively, not at all, somewhat positively, fairly positively, very positively; additional option: I did not help], Default: No answer]

[After Intervention/Mid Time Point]: <for some teams/participants this will start earlier than for others, goal is to have one set of people that is asked about it after ½ of the study, roughly 2 weeks,, the other one after ¾ of it, roughly 4 weeks>

7. How did your team help you to be productive today? [text entry]

[continuing daily questions]

8. How well have you been spending your time today at work?
[7-point Likert-type scale: 1=very poorly, 2=poorly, 3=slightly poorly, 4=neutral, 5=slightly well, 6=well, 7=very well]
9. How would you rate your overall stress level today?
[7-point Likert-type scale: No answer, Very low, Low, Somewhat low, Medium, Somewhat high, High, Very high + option 'not sure']

Location and Work Progress

10. Where did you spend the majority of your time working today?
[3 Options: At the office, At home (remotely), In a different location (remotely)]

11. How many development tasks / issues / user stories / bugs did you work on today? (Note, whatever you use based on your team's practice, it would be great if you keep reporting on the same units.)
[text entry]
12. How many story points did you complete today?
[number entry]
13. How many development tasks / issues / user stories / bugs did you complete today?
[text entry]
14. How many commits did you perform today?
[text entry]
15. Would you like to share anything else about your day?

Weekly Diary

Same questions as Daily Diary, with these additional questions:

16. Rate the following three items:
[7-point Likert-type scale: 1 = strongly disagree; 7 = strongly agree]
 - a) Our team is united in trying to reach its goals for performance
 - b) We all take responsibility for any poor performance by our team
 - c) Our team members have conflicting aspirations for the team's performance
17. How many development tasks / issues / user stories / bugs did you complete/resolve this week? [text entry]
18. How many story points did you complete this week?
[number entry]

Registration Survey

With the shift towards remote/hybrid work and the complex and collaborative nature of software development work, we are conducting a study to examine the interplay between individual and team productivity as well as wellbeing in the workplace. As part of this study, we will give you a smartwatch for the self-reporting that you are allowed to keep at the end, provide you insights into your productivity and wellbeing, and offer a workshop on rethinking stress at the end.

The study is performed by the <Lab Name> at the <University Name> (<UNIVERSITY NAME>) and is planned to run for 6 to 8 weeks. The study will require approximately 15mins of your time per week for the hourly self-reports (on the smartwatch) and the end-of-day surveys (web browser), and additional 75mins for 3 surveys (beginning, mid, and end) and a follow-up interview.

It would be great if you participated in the study. If you are interested, please just fill in the following form. Also, please feel free to contact <PI Name Email> if you have any further questions.

Disclaimer

The <Lab Name> at the <University Name> (<UNIVERSITY NAME>, external research institute), based in <Country> (in the following "<UNIVERSITY NAME>") intends to conduct a study to better understand and support developer productivity and wellbeing in the workplace. In order to participate in the study, you will have to register in the following and accept the consent form provided by <UNIVERSITY NAME>, in which <UNIVERSITY NAME> informs of the data collection methods, the data storage, the confidentiality and retention, the usage of the data, and the data analysis. To conduct the study, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will send a smartwatch to each participant and ask the participant to respond to regular questionnaires on the smartwatch. Additionally, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will conduct online surveys and interviews with the participant (see below the description of the survey).

Please note that your participation in this <UNIVERSITY NAME> study is entirely voluntary. With your participation in the study, you agree to the conditions set by <UNIVERSITY NAME>. You understand and agree that your answers will be collected by <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers, who will analyze the responses. <Company Name> will not provide any information of you to <UNIVERSITY NAME>. Any information you provide to <UNIVERSITY NAME> will be maintained by the involved <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers and hosted on servers of <UNIVERSITY NAME> located in <Country>. A summary report on the

aggregated and anonymized findings (that will not allow identifying you or differentiating between individuals) will be shared with you and <COMPANY NAME>.

1. Please specify your name:
First name: [textbox]
Last name: [textbox]
2. Please specify the email address that you want to use for this study: [textbox]
3. Please specify the team you are working on: [textbox]
4. How many members does the team that you are working on (on a daily basis) have? [number]
5. Please specify the value stream that you are working on: [textbox]
6. Please specify your role:
 - a) Team member
 - b) Tech lead
 - c) Team lead / Counselor
 - d) Scrum master
 - e) Product owner
 - f) Value stream owner
 - g) Other: ...
7. What best describes your field of work?
 - a) Software Development
 - b) Requirements Engineering
 - c) Quality Assurance
 - d) Business Management
 - e) Support & Operations
 - f) Other: ...
8. Please specify if you are an external or internal employee:
 - a) Internal Employee
 - b) External Employee
 - c) Other: ...
9. Consent to Participate in the study: [checkbox]
By checking this box, you confirm that you understand the goal and procedures of the study that the <Lab Name> at the <University Name> is intending to conduct. This includes the collection methods, the data storage, confidentiality and retention, the uses of the data, and the data analysis that are described in the linked Consent Form. Please note that your participation in this <UNIVERSITY NAME> study is entirely voluntary and you are free to withdraw your participation at any point during the study without giving any reason and without any negative consequences. <Company Name> will not provide any information of you to <UNIVERSITY NAME>. Any information you provide to <UNIVERSITY NAME> will be maintained by the involved <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers and hosted on servers of <UNIVERSITY NAME> located in <Country>. A summary report on the aggregated and anonymized findings (that will not allow identifying you or differentiating between individuals) will be shared with you and <COMPANY NAME>. [Consent Form](#)
10. Please let us know if you have any other comments or questions: [textbox]

Thank you so much for your interest in participating in this study.

We will now check if there is a sufficient number of registrations from your team. Once we have a sufficient number of registrations from your team, we will get back to you about the next steps.

It would be great if you could pass on the information about the study and the registration.

If you have any further questions, please feel free to contact me (<PI Name, Email>). Thank you!

Initial Survey

Thank you again for your interest in the study on productivity and wellbeing at work.

To start the study, we would now like to ask you a few questions about your team, your background, and also your smartwatch preferences.

This study is performed by the <Lab Name> at the <University Name>, <Country>. Please feel free to contact me (<PI Name, Email>) if you have any further questions.

Disclaimer

The <Lab Name> at the <University Name> (<UNIVERSITY NAME>, external research institute), based in <Country> (in the following "<UNIVERSITY NAME>") intends to conduct a study to better understand and support developer productivity and wellbeing in the workplace. In order to participate in the study, you will have to register in the following and accept the consent form provided by <UNIVERSITY NAME>, in which <UNIVERSITY NAME> informs of the data collection methods, the data storage, the confidentiality and retention, the usage of the data, and the data analysis. To conduct the study, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will send a smartwatch to each participant and ask the participant to respond to regular questionnaires on the smartwatch. Additionally, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will conduct online surveys and interviews with the participant (see below the description of the survey).

Please note that your participation in this <UNIVERSITY NAME> study is entirely voluntary. With your participation in the study, you agree to the conditions set by <UNIVERSITY NAME>. You understand and agree that your answers will be collected by <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers, who will analyze the responses. <Company Name> will not provide any information of you to <UNIVERSITY NAME>. Any information you provide to <UNIVERSITY NAME> will be maintained by the involved <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers and hosted on servers of <UNIVERSITY NAME> located in <Country>. A summary report on the aggregated and anonymized findings (that will not allow identifying you or differentiating between individuals) will be shared with you and <COMPANY NAME>.

Section A: Team and cohesion

1. How many members does the team that you are working on (on a daily basis) have? [number]
2. How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements? [1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = somewhat disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = somewhat agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree]
 - a) Our team is united in trying to
 - b) We all take responsibility for any poor performance by our
 - c) Our team members have conflicting aspirations for the
 - d) Members of this team stick
 - e) Members of our team would rather go out on their own than
 - f) Our team would like to spend

Section B: Burnout

1. How often does each of the following statements apply to you at work?
[1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = somewhat disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = somewhat agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree]
 - a) I feel burned out from my work
 - b) I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and
 - c) I feel frustrated by my job
 - d) I feel like I'm at the end of my rope

Section C: Participant Information

1. How much professional experience do you have (in years)? [number]
2. How old are you (in years)? [number]
3. Gender: How do you identify?
 - a) Woman
 - b) Man
 - c) Non-binary
 - d) Prefer to self-describe: ...

4. Which of the following smartwatch models would you like for participating in the study? [checkbox]
 - a) Apple Watch SE 44mm aluminum, space grey, black sport wristband
 - b) Apple Watch SE 40mm aluminum, silver, white/polarstern sport wristband
 - c) Samsung Galaxy Watch 4 Classic 42mm black, stainless steel, black wrist band
 - d) Samsung Galaxy Watch 4 Classic 42mm silver, stainless steel, white wrist band
 - e) Other Samsung Galaxy Watch 4 or Apple Watch SE model (maximum value CHF 350), please specify model, size, color, band and provide a link to the website for purchasing it (e.g. apple, digitec, or microspot) below.
 - f) Don't need a watch, I have my own.
2. If you want a model different from the four default choices, please specify the model, size, color, band, band size and provide a link to the website for purchasing it. Please note that the maximum value for the model is CHF 350 and it has to be either a Samsung Galaxy Watch 4 or an Apple Watch SE model. [textbox]
3. If you selected an Apple SE smartwatch, please specify the size of the wristband: [number]
4. If you selected a Samsung Galaxy Watch 4 smartwatch, please specify the size of the wristband: [number]
5. Which address would you like the smartwatch to be delivered to? [textboxes for name and address]
6. If you have your own watch, please specify the model so we can ensure compatibility: [textbox]

Thank you so much for filling out this survey and for participating in this study. We really appreciate it. We will order the watch for you, send you the tutorial for setting up the self-reporting application on the smartwatch, and contact you about the start date.

If you have any further questions, please feel free to contact me (<PI Name, Email>). Thank you!

Midpoint Survey

Thank you again for your interest in the study on productivity and wellbeing at work.

Now that you are roughly at the midpoint of the study, we would like to ask you again a few questions about your team.

This study is performed by the <Lab Name> at the <University Name>, <Country>. Please feel free to contact me (<PI Name, Email>) if you have any further questions.

Disclaimer

The <Lab Name> at the <University Name> (<UNIVERSITY NAME>, external research institute), based in <Country> (in the following "<UNIVERSITY NAME>") intends to conduct a study to better understand and support developer productivity and wellbeing in the workplace. In order to participate in the study, you will have to register in the following and accept the consent form provided by <UNIVERSITY NAME>, in which <UNIVERSITY NAME> informs of the data collection methods, the data storage, the confidentiality and retention, the usage of the data, and the data analysis. To conduct the study, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will send a smartwatch to each participant and ask the participant to respond to regular questionnaires on the smartwatch. Additionally, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will conduct online surveys and interviews with the participant (see below the description of the survey).

Please note that your participation in this <UNIVERSITY NAME> study is entirely voluntary. With your participation in the study, you agree to the conditions set by <UNIVERSITY NAME>. You understand and agree that your answers will be collected by <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers, who will analyze the responses. <Company Name> will not provide any information of you to <UNIVERSITY NAME>. Any information you provide to <UNIVERSITY NAME> will be maintained by the involved <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers and hosted on servers of <UNIVERSITY NAME> located in <Country>. A summary report on the aggregated and anonymized findings (that will not allow identifying you or differentiating between individuals) will be shared with you and <COMPANY NAME>.

Section A: Team and Cohesion

1. How many members does the team that you are working on (on a daily basis) have? [number]
2. Has your team changed over the first part of the study, and if so, how? [textbox]
3. How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements? [1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = somewhat disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = somewhat agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree]
 - g) Our team is united in trying to
 - h) We all take responsibility for any poor performance by our
 - i) Our team members have conflicting aspirations for the
 - j) Members of this team stick
 - k) Members of our team would rather go out on their own than
 - l) Our team would like to spend
4. Have your team interactions changed over the first part of the study, and if so, how? [textbox]
5. How do you generally prioritize the work/tasks that you are working on? [textbox]
6. Are you often faced with too many requests from other teams / the organization, and if so, what do you do in that situation? [textbox]

Section B: Burnout

1. How often does each of the following statements apply to you at work?
[1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = somewhat disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = somewhat agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree]
 - e) I feel burned out from my work
 - f) I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and
 - g) I feel frustrated by my job
 - h) I feel like I'm at the end of my rope

Thank you so much for filling out this survey and for participating in this study. We really appreciate it.

If you have any further questions, please feel free to contact us (<PI Name, Email>). Thank you!

Final Survey

Thank you so much for your participation in the study on productivity and wellbeing at work.

You are almost at the end of the study, and we would like to ask you to fill out the following survey about your team, the study, and your personality. The survey will take about 20 to 30 minutes of your time and we would highly appreciate your responses.

This study is performed by the <Lab Name> at the <University Name>, <Country>. Please feel free to contact us (<PI Name, Email>) if you have any further questions.

Disclaimer

The <Lab Name> at the <University Name> (<UNIVERSITY NAME>, external research institute), based in <Country> (in the following "<UNIVERSITY NAME>") intends to conduct a study to better understand and support developer productivity and wellbeing in the workplace. In order to participate in the study, you will have to register in the following and accept the consent form provided by <UNIVERSITY NAME>, in which <UNIVERSITY NAME> informs of the data collection methods, the data storage, the confidentiality and retention, the usage of the data, and the data analysis. To conduct the study, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will send a smartwatch to each participant and ask the participant to respond to regular questionnaires on the smartwatch. Additionally, <UNIVERSITY NAME> will conduct online surveys and interviews with the participant (see below the description of the survey).

Please note that your participation in this <UNIVERSITY NAME> study is entirely voluntary. With your participation in the study, you agree to the conditions set by <UNIVERSITY NAME>. You understand and agree that your answers will be collected by <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers, who will analyze the responses. <Company Name> will not provide any information of you to <UNIVERSITY NAME>. Any information you provide to <UNIVERSITY NAME> will be maintained by the involved <UNIVERSITY NAME> researchers and hosted on servers of <UNIVERSITY NAME> located in <Country>. A summary report on the aggregated and anonymized findings (that will not allow identifying you or differentiating between individuals) will be shared with you and <COMPANY NAME>.

Section A: Team and Cohesion

1. How many members does the team that you are working on (on a daily basis) have? [number]
2. Has your team changed over the first part of the study, and if so, how? [textbox]
3. How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements? [1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = somewhat disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = somewhat agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree]
 - m) Our team is united in trying to
 - n) We all take responsibility for any poor performance by our
 - o) Our team members have conflicting aspirations for the
 - p) Members of this team stick
 - q) Members of our team would rather go out on their own than
 - r) Our team would like to spend
4. Have your team interactions changed over the first part of the study, and if so, how? [textbox]
5. How do you generally prioritize the work/tasks that you are working on? [textbox]
6. Are you often faced with too many requests from other teams / the organization, and if so, what do you do in that situation? [textbox]
7. How does helping members of your team impact you and your individual productivity? [textbox]
8. How does your team help you to be productive? [textbox]
9. Does your definition of your team overlap with the team(s) defined by the organization, and if not, how does it differ? [textbox]

Section B: Burnout

1. How often does each of the following statements apply to you at work?
[1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = somewhat disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = somewhat agree, 6 = agree, 7 = strongly agree]
 - i) I feel burned out from my work
 - j) I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and

- k) I feel frustrated by my job
- l) I feel like I'm at the end of my rope

Section C: Intervention and Retrospection

1. Has the reflection on your team's help changed your perspective on your team or the interaction with your team, and if so how? [textbox]
2. Was the reflection on your own work and productivity helpful to you and if so, in which way? [textbox]
3. Did you also participate in the "upskilling as a team" program and if so, when did you start this? [textbox]
4. Was the reflection on your time well spent at work helpful to you and if so why? [textbox]
5. Are there any further comments you have for the study, your participation or more general? [textbox]

Section D: Personality

1. Here are a number of personality traits that may or may not apply to you. Please write a number next to each statement to indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with that statement. You should rate the extent to which the pair of traits applies to you, even if one characteristic applies more strongly than the other.

I see myself as... [1 = disagree strongly, 2 = disagree moderately, 3 = disagree a little, 4 = neither agree nor disagree, 5 = agree a little, 6 = agree moderately, 7 = agree strongly]

- a) ...reserved
- b) ...talkative
- c) ...assertive
- d) ...bold
- e) ...introverted
- f) ...energetic
- g) ...agreeable
- h) ...cooperative
- i) ...considerate
- j) ...organized
- k) ...dependable
- l) ...conscientious
- m) ...relaxed
- n) ...touchy
- o) ...moody
- p) ...emotional
- q) ...high-strung
- r) ...calm
- s) ...imaginative
- t) ...creative
- u) ...intellectual
- v) ...cold
- w) ...helpful
- x) ...rude
- y) ...shallow
- z) ...complex
- aa) ...sloppy
- bb) ...careless
- cc) ...systematic
- dd) ...extraverted
- ee) ...shy
- ff) ...quiet
- gg) ...verbal
- hh) ...anxious
- ii) ...unenvious
- jj) ...unemotional
- kk) ...temperamental
- ll) ...unsympathetic
- mm) ...kind
- nn) ...warm

- oo) ...sympathetic
- pp) ...efficient
- qq) ...neat
- rr) ...disorganized
- ss) ...thorough
- tt) ...unintellectual
- uu) ...unimaginative
- vv) ...artistic
- ww) ...philosophical

Thank you so much for filling out this survey and for participating in this study. We really appreciate it.

We will send you an email soon with final remarks. We might also contact you to ask if you are willing to participate in a short interview to gather some more in-depth feedback.

At this point, you can stop the self-reporting on the smartwatch and also uninstall the application completely. If you wish to continue, you can still do so.

If you have any further questions or feedback, please feel free to contact us (<PI Name, Email). Thank you!

Final Interview

Semi-structured interview guideline

Individual Work & Productivity

1. Could you describe the nature of your work?
2. Has the nature of your work changed since you started the study and if so how?
3. [survey, check] How do you generally prioritize the work/tasks that you are working on?
4. [survey, check] Are you often faced with too many requests from other teams / the organization and if so, from whom?
 - a) What do you do in that situation?
 - b) How does it affect your work?
5. [Survey, check answers before] How do you assess your own productivity?
6. [Survey, check answers before] What factors do you think are most important to your own productivity?
7. [optional?] What would you say are the criteria your manager uses to assess your productivity?

Teams and Team Productivity

8. Could you describe your team, and how do you define your team?
9. [survey, check] Does your description/definition of your team overlap with the team(s) defined by the organization, and if not, how does it differ?
10. Do you often help your team members during your work day?
 - a) If so how? What are the most common scenarios?
 - b) How does it affect your work?
 - c) Are there common cases in which helping your team affects your productivity negatively, and if so, when?
 - d) Are there common cases in which helping your team affects your productivity positively, and if so, when?
 - e) [survey check] How does it affect your individual productivity?
11. Do you also often ask your team members for help?
 - a) If so how? What are the most common scenarios?
 - b) How does that affect your productivity?
 - c) [survey] How does your team help you to be productive?
 - d) More generally, when you need help for a task, how do you usually go about it, do you ask your team, consult Q&A websites,...? And why?
12. How do you go about assessing your team's productivity?
13. How do you stay aware of your team?
14. Are you aware of your organizational goals? What are they?
15. Do you often think about the goals of your organization?
16. Are your organizational goals aligned with your own goals, and how so?

Intervention and Retrospection

17. [survey, check] Was the reflection on your own work and productivity helpful to you and if so, in which way?
18. [survey, check] Was the reflection on your time well spent at work helpful to you and if so why?
19. How was it to reflect on your productivity and time well spend on your watch?
20. [survey, check] Has the reflection on your team's help changed your perspective on your team or the interaction with your team, and if so how?
21. Did you notice that the questions of the end of day survey changed?
22. Did this change on the focus on how your team helped you instead of just how you helped your team changed your perspective in any way?
23. Are there any further comments you have for the study, your participation or more general?